

Italy (Milano region) Partner Services: Standard Operating Procedure

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Contentss

Introduction	3
Purpose	3
Background	3
Definitions.....	3
Indications for PN.....	4
Timing of PN.....	4
Look-back Intervals By Disease	4
Contraindications	4
IPV assessment:	5
Procedure.....	5
Methods.....	5
HIV/STIs.....	5
Overview	5
Detailed.....	6
Viral Hepatitis.....	6
Overview	6
Detailed.....	6
TB	6
Overview	6
Detailed.....	7
Legal	7
National regulations.....	7
GDPR	8
Protecting the Patient.....	9
Interview	9
Tools.....	9
Scripts.....	9
ICT tools	9
Monitoring	10
Annexes.....	10
Annex A: Glossary	10
Annex B: Lookback Intervals	10
Annex C: IPV Screening Tool	11

Annex D: Flowcharts and Infographics	12
HIV/STIs.....	12
TB	12
Annex E: Healthcare Professional PN Talking Points	12
Annex F: Patient PN Scripts.....	13
Talking Points for Patients	13
Example Letter for Patient Use	14
Anonymous Example Letter for Patient Use.....	15

Introduction

Purpose

This document describes the standard procedure for partner notification/ contact tracing services in Italy.

The guidelines and recommendations in this manual are not intended to be set in stone. They are designed to be updated and expanded on as necessary and as changes in medical practice and legislation arise.

Background

WHO notes that partner notification is an important public health approach in infectious disease management. Partner notification has clinical benefits – it aims to prevent re-infection of the index patient and treat their sexual and needle-injecting partners and close contacts – as well as public health benefits – it aims to control the spread of infectious diseases and reduce infectious disease related morbidity and mortality. It is also a key strategy for reaching infected people who are asymptomatic and people who do not present for diagnosis, counselling and treatment. There are different approaches to partner notification, which can be broadly defined as patient referral, provider referral, and contract or conditional referral.

Assisted partner notification has been an important public health approach in infectious disease management for decades, including in programmes targeting sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and tuberculosis (TB). STI partner notification approaches have been shown to be effective in diagnosing and treating STIs and preventing recurrent infection. Likewise, active tracing of contacts and the voluntary screening of household members of people with active TB is an effective and standard approach that has been used successfully in communities with high HIV and TB prevalence.

Definitions

Partner notification, or disclosure, or contact tracing, is defined as a voluntary process whereby a trained provider asks people diagnosed with an infectious disease about their sexual partners and/or drug injecting partners and then, if the diagnosed patient agrees, offers these partners HTS. Partner notification is provided using passive or assisted approaches (WHO, 2015). In this manual, partner notification will be used in place of contact tracing, even though in some disease areas this will refer to contacting individuals that are not ‘partners’ of the index patient.

Passive partner notification services refer to when diagnosed patients are encouraged by a trained provider to disclose their status to their sexual and/ or drug injecting partners by themselves, and to also suggest HTS to the partner(s) given their potential exposure to infection.

Assisted partner notification services refer to when consenting diagnosed patients are assisted by a trained provider to disclose their status or to anonymously notify their sexual and/or drug injecting partner(s) of their potential exposure to infection. The provider then offers testing to these partner(s). Assisted partner notification is done using provider referral or dual referral approaches.

Provider referral: With the consent of the infected patient, a trained provider confidentially contacts the person's partner(s) directly and offers the partner(s) voluntary HTS. In many countries, this is only permissible after the involvement of legal or public health committees.

Please see Annex A for a complete glossary of terms.

Indications for PN

Timing of PN

According to the WHO, partner notification services should be offered as part of a comprehensive package of testing and care. While patients should promptly be offered voluntary partner services, it is important to remember that a patient may not be ready to disclose their status upon receiving the diagnosis. For this reason, patients should be offered partner services throughout their interaction with the health system, from diagnosis, to enrolment in treatment, and any follow up visits (WHO, 2016).

Look-back Intervals By Disease

The appropriate look-back interval for partner services should be used. The look-back interval is the time during which the index case may have been infectious and transmitted infection, and should be applied to all contacts whether or not protection was used. The table below lists the infections for which PN should be offered contact actions agreed with the index case, and followed up by a HCW with the appropriate documented competency (Annex B). The corresponding look-back intervals, and whether or not epidemiological treatment of contacts is recommended, is also given. However, these look-back intervals are for guidance. Every case should be assessed on the basis of the sexual history, risk assessment and particular circumstances. There may be benefit in offering PN for some contacts outside these look-back intervals, and justification for not offering PN within the specified intervals.

Contraindications

While partner notification is an important prevention method, there may be situations in which it is not safe for a patient to disclose to their partners, including in the case of minors. If the patient has any concerns of violence, healthcare workers should utilise the intimate partner violence (IPV) screening tool to help assess if partner notification should proceed (Annex C).

IPV assessment:

With the patient, the healthcare worker/ designated staff member should review any partners where there is a risk or concern of violence. An example of initiate partner violence includes the following questions:

1. Has [partner's name] ever hit, kicked, slapper or otherwise physically hurt you?
2. Has [partner's name] ever threatened to hurt you?
3. Has [partner's name] ever forced you to do something sexually that made you uncomfortable?
4. Do/ did you generally feel physically or emotionally unsafe in your relationship with [partner's name]?

If the patient answers “yes” to any of these screening questions, then consider not performing partner notification services and instead explore other approaches.

Procedure

This section describes the process of partner notification by disease area. It includes an overview of the partner notification pathways, information on the legal restrictions for partner notification, description of the partner notification interview and tools for healthcare providers and patients.

Methods

This section describes the pathways for partner notification in Italy by disease areas. All infographics for the following section can be found in Annex D.

HIV/STIs

Overview

Below is an overview of the PN pathways for HIV/STIs in Italy.

*Not valid in all regions

*PN performed by public health units is not utilized/ available in all regions.

Detailed

There are no national guidelines for HIV/STI PN. Particularly due to the structure of healthcare systems in Italy, there is significant regional variation in PN. In the Milan region, HIV/STIs are reported to local public health units anonymously. In some regions (Verona), specially trained nurses and doctors manage STI diagnoses and support patients in PN. Patient referral is preferred and the most common, typically PN done through phone calls, text messages and in person.

For HIV, patients are responsible for contacting partners and doctors can play a supportive role. If the patient agrees, the doctor can inform partners if the patient is in the room with them. Trained CBVCT employees can lead community-assisted PN. As of November 2018, the National AIDS Plan is under discussion, and may allow doctors to notify partners after receiving authorization from a Privacy Guarantor.

In some regions, the public health service of local authority can contact the diagnosing doctor to see if PN has been done. If PN is not completed, the local authority can request the name of the diagnosed patient and initiate PN themselves (unknown how common this is).

Viral Hepatitis

Overview

There are no national guidelines for viral hepatitis PN, and no established pathways for the PN process.

Detailed

There are no national guidelines for viral hepatitis PN. In the case of viral hepatitis, it is suggested to follow the European guidelines (***)The patient must be responsible for partner notification. Doctors may play a supportive role and present the various available PN tools for the patient to use. Legally, doctors may not disclose a patient's status unless the patient is in the room.

TB

Overview

Below is an overview of the referral pathway for TB contact tracing.

Detailed

Tuberculosis is transmitted through droplets released into the air via coughs and sneezes, and does not require any physical contact to spread disease. For this reason the process of informing contacts differs significantly in the case of TB. Instead of only notifying sexual and needle-sharing partners, TB contact tracing must also screen household and close contacts of TB patients. The screening and testing guidelines can be found in 'The Protocol for Clinical Management of Tuberculosis' and is managed by public health authorities.

Contact tracing is handled by local public health who interview patients and construct a list of contacts. In TB clinics, contact tracing is done by a health assistant (who has a 3-4 year degree and specific training in CT) who does epidemiological surveillance. Outside of TB clinics, doctors are responsible for CT which adds to their already heavy workload. When TB patients are admitted to the hospital, the assistants come to the ward to do a survey. Patients give information about their close community and the assistant traces the contacts. Tracing is usually done by phone and the assistant does not do house visits.

Legal

National regulations

HIV testing activities must be carried out in compliance with the rules set forth in the consent document on "Policies and methodologies regulating HIV testing in Italy" (Rep. N. 134/CSR 27 Jul 2011) (11A11001) (G.U. Serie Generale n. 191 8 Aug 2011, <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.biz/atti/2011/20110191/11A11001.htm>)

Art. 5 c. 1 of Law 135/90 ensures anonymity and non-discrimination to all PLHIV.

Art. 10 of the present CdM specifies that: "clinician must keep the secrecy/confidentiality on all the information that they get to know during their professional activities...disclosure is allowed if motivated by a just cause, represented by the fulfillment of an obligation established by law (report

to the Judicial Authority, health complaints, notifications of infectious diseases, mandatory certifications) or from the provisions of subsequent articles 11 (Confidentiality of personal data) and 12 (Processing of personal data).” This means that physicians can only disclose patient status in rare cases that will allow it “to be considered exempt to the extent to which facing the risk of contagion deriving from a rare venereal disease, they consider as prevalent the interest of the patients partners’ health or the community health” possibly after being granted authorization by the Privacy Guarantor.

GDPR

The General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 is a regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy for all individuals within the European Union and the European Economic Area. It also addresses the export of personal data outside the EU and EEA areas.

Article 9 of the GDPR specifically addresses health data (see below).

Article 9

Processing of special categories of personal data

1. Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.

The GDPR prohibition on health data, does not apply under certain conditions, such as the following:

2. Paragraph 1 shall not apply if one of the following applies:

(a) the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specified purposes, except where Union or Member State law provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject;

....

(h) processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, **the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of Union or Member State law** or pursuant to contract with a health professional and subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 3;

(i) **processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health** or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy.

As Italian law does not allow healthcare providers or trained staff to notify a patient’s partner (unless in the case of TB), the GDPR does not affect the process of partner notification. It is important to remember that healthcare providers (HCPs)/ trained staff can still inform patients of multiple methods available for their use in PN, including phone calls, emails, ICT tools and other resources. Patients are legally allowed to utilize any of these methods in patient referral, where they notify their partners without the involvement of HCPs.

NOTE: It is important to clarify the legalities of recording/managing partner contact details under the GDPR with your organization.

Protecting the Patient

It is important to make patients aware of their duty to protect future partners from the risk of transmission.

Interview

The Interview for partner notification should include the follow topics:

I. Introduction a. Introduce yourself b. State purpose/role c. Explain confidentiality
II. Patient Assessment a. Patient Concerns b. Social History c. Medical History d. Disease Comprehension
III. Disease Intervention a. Partner Discussion b. Intimate Partner Violence Screening c. Partner Notification Plan d. Risk Reduction
IV. Conclusion and Summary

During the interview, healthcare professionals and designated staff will elicit information about the patients' sex, needle-sharing and close contacts as appropriate. They will assess for intimate partner violence (Annex C) and discuss and establish a partner notification plan with the patient. For additional guidance, more detailed talking points have been provided in Annex E for use by healthcare professionals and designated staff. This script is a guide and may be changed to fit specific needs/ contexts.

Tools

There are many tools available for patients to help them approach partner notification. These tools vary, allowing patients to notify partners through anonymous methods and ICT tools as well as more traditional methods.

Scripts

Whether the patient decides to notify partners in person, via SMS, phone call, letter or email, it can still be difficult to begin the conversation. There are many resources that offer example scripts for patients to use. Annex F includes some examples.

ICT tools

Some key populations may feel more comfortable utilizing ICT tools to notify partners. There are many to choose from, with many allowing the patient to remain completely anonymous. The EU joint action INTEGRATE has created a free online tool which can be found on the website [***](#). Other options, such as websites or apps, can be found in Annex F.

Monitoring

The ECDC recommends monitoring partner notification practices through clinical audits in order to develop interventions that improve outcomes (ECDC, 2015). INTEGRATE experts have suggested gathering data on the following indicators:

- % of patients with PN discussion done
- Proportion of index patients with persistent or recurrent infections

The ECDC also recommends monitoring the following indicators, but there are legal and practical constraints to doing so. Where possible try to gather the following:

- # of partners notified per index patient
- # and proportion of traceable partners per index patient
- # and proportion of partners contacted (mean, reported by index patient)
- # of partners attending clinic per index patient
- # and proportion of partners tested per index patient
- # and proportion of partners infected of the total # of contacts tested
- # of newly infected partners per index patient
- # and proportion of (infected) partners treated of the total numbers of partners infected
- # of partners treated per index patient

For information on TB monitoring, refer to the national guidelines.

Annexes

[Annex A: Glossary](#)

[Annex B: Lookback Intervals](#)

Look-back Intervals by Infection

Infection	Look-back Intervals for PN
Anogenital Warts	6 months
Chancroid	10 days
Chlamydial Infection	Males with urethral symptoms: 4 weeks All other cases: 6 months
Epididymo-orchitis	6 months
Gonorrhoea	Males with urethral symptoms: 2 weeks All other cases: 3 months
Hepatitis A	According to estimated time of infection or 2 weeks before the onset of jaundice If suspected outbreak or concerns of food/water infection, notify local CDC
Hepatitis B 	According to estimated time of infection (via sex or injection) or 2 weeks before the onset of jaundice Screen unvaccinated children born to infectious female index cases.
Hepatitis C 	As far back as estimated time of infection (via sex or injection) if index case and/or contact is HIV positive Ensure any children of female index case are tested.
HIV infection	3 months in recent infection or since last negative HIV test or as far back as required if untested. Ongoing PN should include discussion about testing and re-testing of current partners and testing of children, where appropriate
LGV infection	4 weeks

Non-specific (nonchlamydial, nongonococcal) urethritis in men	Males with symptoms: 4 weeks
Pelvic inflammatory disease	6 months
Phthirus pubis infestation	3 months
Scabies infestation	2 months (including household, prolonged skin-to-skin and bed and clothes sharing contacts)
Syphilis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary syphilis: 3 months o Secondary and early latent syphilis: 2 years o Late latent and late syphilis: (of sexual partners and children of female patients) back to the date of the last negative syphilis serology, if available, OR back over the patient's sexual lifetime as far as is feasible.
Trichomoniasis	4 weeks (ISUTI recommends 2 months)

Annex C: IPV Screening Tool

The following IPV screening tool was created using AIDSfree resources

With the patient, the healthcare worker/ designated staff member should review any partners where there is a risk or concern of violence. The screening for intimate partner violence includes four questions:

1. Has [partner's name] ever hit, kicked, slapper or otherwise physically hurt you?
2. Has [partner's name] ever threatened to hurt you?
3. Has [partner's name] ever forced you to do something sexually that made you uncomfortable?
4. Do/ did you generally feel physically or emotionally unsafe in your relationship with [partner's name]?

If the patient answers "yes" to any of these screening questions, then consider not performing partner notification services and instead explore other approaches.

Annex D: Flowcharts and Infographics

HIV/STIs

*Not valid in all regions

TB

Annex E: Healthcare Professional PN Talking Points

Talking points taken from AIDSfree resources

During post-test counselling and/or counselling in the (HIV/STI/hepatitis) clinic:

- Explain the importance of ensuring that all partners get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis).
 - (HIV/STI/hepatitis) infected partners can start on (HIV/STI/hepatitis) treatment to keep them healthy and reduce risk that they will pass (HIV/STI/hepatitis) to other sex partners and/or children.
 - Partners not infected with (HIV/STI/hepatitis) can access prevention services to help them remain uninfected, including condoms, pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP), and male circumcision.
- Inform the index client that:
 - The clinic is offering Partner Testing Services to assist the client to contact their partners so that these partners can learn their (HIV/STI/hepatitis) status.
 - The service is offered because we know disclosure of (HIV/STI/hepatitis) status to partners can be difficult.
 - Discuss the potential contacts, both sexual and needle sharing, that the patient may need to contact.
- Remind the client of the importance of partner testing using information from above.
- Inform the client that there are options for contacting partners:
 - Client can contact the partner and let them know they should be tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis);
 - The healthcare providers can contact the partners directly, without telling them the client's name (this will be done anonymously);
 - The counsellor/provider can sit with the client and his/her partner and support the client as he or she tells the partner about their (HIV/STI/hepatitis) infection.
- Inform the index client that:
 - All information will be kept confidential. This means that:
 - Partners will NOT be told the index client's name or test results.
 - The index client will NOT be told the (HIV/STI/hepatitis) test results of their partner(s) or whether or not their partner(s) actually tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis).
 - You will NOT contact the partner without first contacting them to get their permission.
 - They will continue to receive the same level of care at this health facility regardless of whether they choose to participate in partner notification services.
- Discuss the need to protect future partners from the risk of transmission
- Answer any questions that the index client might have and obtain verbal consent to continue.

Annex F: Patient PN Scripts

Talking Points for Patients

Make a Plan:

- Many people are afraid of telling their partner that they have (HIV/STI/hepatitis). It is helpful to make a plan

for how and when you will tell your partner.

- Think about how you would like to be told, if your partner was disclosing to you.
- Choose a day and a time when you and your partner will have time to talk.
- You also want to pick a time when your partner is not stressed or angry, and has not been

drinking alcohol.

- Pick a private place where you feel comfortable and safe. You may want to have someone in the next room to help and support you, if needed.

Anticipate Reactions:

- Think about how your partner may react. Your partner may:
 - o Offer you support or comfort you
 - o Not believe it's true
 - o Feel confused or sad
 - o Feel angry
 - o Accuse you of bringing (HIV/STI/hepatitis) into the relationship or household
- Think about how you will respond to these reactions.
- What questions may your partner ask you? How will you answer these questions?

Start the Conversation:

- "I went to the clinic for a check-up the other day [or for xyz reason] and the doctor/nurse was encouraging people to get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis). So I got tested and learned that I have (HIV/STI/hepatitis). I wanted you to know so that you could also get an (HIV/STI/hepatitis) test. [If HIV] There are medicines now for treating HIV that can help us live a long time."
- "(HIV/STI/hepatitis) is very common in our community. I decided to go for an (HIV/STI/hepatitis) test. It turns out that I have (HIV/STI/hepatitis). I already started on treatment. I think it is important that you also get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis) so you can know your (HIV/STI/hepatitis) status."

Encourage Your Partner to Get Tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis):

- Give your partner the Referral Slip
- Tell your partner that it is important they get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis). If they have (HIV/STI/hepatitis), they can get medicines to treat their (HIV/STI/hepatitis). These medicines can save their life and reduce the chance they will pass (HIV/STI/hepatitis) onto others.
- If they do not have (HIV/STI/hepatitis), there are things they can do to help them remain uninfected like use condoms, take pre-exposure prophylaxis, or get circumcised (if they are male).
- Offer support because this is difficult news for someone to hear. "We can work on this together. I will support you".

Practice First!

- Practice what you will say and do ahead of time. You can do that now with your health care provider or later by yourself in your home. This will help you feel comfortable on the day you actually tell your partner.

Example Letter for Patient Use

Here is an example letter for Chlamydia. More STI specific letter examples and fact sheets found at www.letthemknow.org.au .

Dear _____

Since I last saw you I've been told that I have Chlamydia. It's an infection that's passed on through sex. So, you might have this infection too. Even if you don't have any symptoms you can still have the infection.

The only way to be sure you are OK is to get tested and treated by your doctor. The treatment is easy and effective.

It's important to get checked because, if left untreated, Chlamydia can cause long-term health problems such as infertility.

I've included a fact sheet on Chlamydia and a letter you can take along to your doctor. If you want to know more you can visit this website www.letthemknow.org.au/partners.html

If you live in _____ call the Sexual Health Infoline on _____ to speak to a sexual health nurse.

Sorry to give you this news but I'm concerned about your health and I thought it was better that you knew.

Regards

Anonymous Example Letter for Patient Use

Here is an example anonymous letter for Gonorrhoea. More STI specific letter examples and fact sheets found at www.letthemknow.org.au.

Dear _____

This letter has been sent to you because someone you have had sex with has gonorrhoea.

Gonorrhoea is a bacterial infection that can be passed from one person to another through sexual contact.

You may have gonorrhoea even though you don't have any symptoms. The only way to find out for certain is to be tested by a doctor.

Gonorrhoea is usually easily treated and we suggest you have the treatment even if your test shows you don't have the infection.

We have attached a fact sheet on gonorrhoea and a letter you can take to your doctor.

Please don't ignore this letter because, if gonorrhoea is not treated it could cause painful medical complications for you. www.letthemknow.org.au/partners.html

If you live in _____ call the Sexual Health Infoline on _____ speak to a sexual health nurse.

Sorry to give you this news but I'm concerned about your health and I thought it was better that you knew.

Regards